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M2.3 Third open call for financial support launched

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1 Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	30.09.2024	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)	TOC and V0.1
0.2	24.09.30	Lisa de Leeuw (DANS)	review of v0.1
1.0	24.09.30	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)	updated version for publication

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
TRUST-GRANTS	Dedicated platform for applicants to the FAIR-IMPACT open calls operated by Trust-IT

3 Introduction

One of the goals of the FAIR-IMPACT project is to support the implementation and adoption of FAIR-enabling practices, tools and services across scientific communities at European, national and institutional level. It has done so through a series of open calls for cascading funding and in-kind support. Five open calls for support have been launched over the life of the project. This brief milestone report provides details of the third open call for financial support and related promotional activities.

4 Description of the Milestone

4.1 Role of the milestone

This milestone report provides evidence that the third open call for financial support was launched via the FAIR-IMPACT website as planned on 30 September 2024. A news item was added to the FAIR-IMPACT website to announce the launch¹. The report also provides details on dissemination and other relevant activities related to the open call, as well as a brief summary of next steps.

4.1.1 Means of verification

Information about the open call was published via the website on 30 September² outlining **four support actions** with links to further information about the action and the timelines for the support actions to be delivered.

#1 Managing data types, schemas and vocabularies and crosswalks for FAIR researcher related metadata³

The support action will introduce successful applicants to three tools developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC (FC4E) project. These include the Data Type Registry (DTR), vocabulary service, and Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR).

In this support action the participants will use one or more of the FC4E tools to enhance the machine-actionability of their existing schema and crosswalk specifications. This could mean for example the registration of schema from public APIs to the MSCR and creation of mappings from those service specific data models to common formats such as Datacite and DCAT or creating a metadata schema using enriched schema elements registered in the DTR.

Successful applicants will receive 5000 € to support their participation.

#2: Creating EOSC compliant interoperability policies based on EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF)⁴

One of the main concerns when we deploy a service, especially those related to data, is how this service can work with others. This is relevant for services to be integrated in the EOSC ecosystem. The creation of the EOSC IF is an effort to analyse the gaps and problems addressed in this context. Also, it provides recommendations to improve this integration. One of the main challenges is to translate these recommendations into specific actions. This question is addressed in the work being done by FAIR IMPACT in the context of the production of interoperability guidelines.

¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/news/fair-impact-third-open-call-support-cascading-grants>

² <https://fair-impact.eu/3rd-open-call-route-2-support-opens-30-sept>

³ <https://fair-impact.eu/managing-data-schemas-vocabularies>

⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/creating-eosc-compliant-interoperability-policies>

In this support action, successful applicants will analyse the interoperability status of their services using tools such as F-UJI and CAT. After this analysis, we will identify actions that they can carry out to improve the interoperability of their services based on the guidelines provided.

Successful applicants will receive 5000 € to support their participation.

#3: Testing the trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories prototype⁵

FAIR-enabling and trustworthy data repositories play a central role in making and keeping data FAIR over time. While there is ongoing debate on what constitutes trustworthiness, there is broad agreement that transparency and evidence is essential to enable end users to make informed decisions about the repository services they use. In this support action successful applicants will have the opportunity to test a prototype developed by FAIR-IMPACT to expose relevant metadata at the organisational and object level.

Successful applicants will receive 5000 € to support their participation.

#4: Implementation of a shared API for semantic catalogues⁶

A lot of valuable information in the form of ontologies, vocabularies, etc. are publicly available and are contained in numerous catalogues. Our aim is to facilitate increasing the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) of these catalogues via the use of a common data model to describe the holdings of the catalogues as well as the adoption of a common Application Programming Interface (API) to query the catalogues.

We invite Semantic Artefact Catalogue (SAC) providers to apply to join this support action to implement an API based on the Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication (MOD) ontology to promote interoperability and enhance access to SACs. This API enables a uniform interface to semantic artefacts (SA), enabling seamless querying by stakeholders, regardless of domain. This open call is an opportunity for SACs to participate in a community-driven effort to improve the FAIRness of their resources through the adoption of this API.

Successful applicants will receive 8000 € to support their participation.

⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/testing-tdr-and-fair-enabling-prototype>

⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementing-shared-api-for-semantic-catalogues>

5 Next steps

FAIR-IMPACT will be actively promoting the final open call for financial support via the project newsletters, social media channels (Twitter⁷, LinkedIn⁸) and via the EOSC Forum⁹.

FAIR-IMPACT will run an introductory webinar on 9 October¹⁰ to describe the support actions and to answer any initial questions from potential applicants. A virtual clinic will be held on 13 November to allow potential applicants to be able to ask any questions they have about the support programmes, their applications, eligibility, and the evaluation process.

Figure 1. Introductory webinar for potential applicants

Open Call WEBINAR

**Final Open Call for Support
Route 2: Cascading Grants**

14:00 - 15.00 CEST - 9 October 2024

FAIR Implementation Team *Online*

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Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC

FAIR-IMPACT.eu

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Evaluation and selection of successful applicants will be carried out during December and applicants will be informed of the outcome by 8 January 2025. The support actions will kick off in late January/early February 2025 and run to April 2025.

⁷ https://twitter.com/fairimpact_eu

⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fair-impact-eu-project/>

⁹ <https://forum.eosc.eu/message/64270414686177ebd9758807>

¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impacts-final-open-call-financial-support>